

Combating gender stereotypes by highlighting women's contribution to the history of societies

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HerStory Pilot Implementation

HerStory Map Excursion Guidelines for Velenje (Slovenia)

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HerStory Consortium

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1. Introduction

The current document is developed to provide guidelines on tour excursion development, for monuments of women in local history and to ensure that the experience is educational, engaging, and respectful, a set of best approaches is presented below, to select the most suitable for each country.

The first phase of excursion will take place at a pilot phase with 160 persons in total (at least in the pilot excursion), so **20 people from each country**, and at least half of the total (**10**) **must be Young people**. Following to the excursion, all partners will collect the feedback, make the necessary changes, and then prepare another excursion, the final one.

Final excursion will involve 160 persons in total (at least in the excursion), so **20 people from each country**, and least half of the total (**10**) **must be Young people**. At the end a total of 320 participants (as a minimum), at least half of the total (160) must be young people.

The participants of the excursions will consist of young people and educators, trainers and academics:

- young people, boys, and girls
- young people active in local community groups such as Municipalities' Youth Councils
- students from the fields of History
- students from the fields of Gender Studies
- youth experts
- youth organizations
- Academics from the fields of History and Gender Studies
- Teachers and educators
- Teachers, and women and human rights organizations experts/activists

Each partner will create different and specific activities for the excursions organized in their city, for the pilots and the final ones. A set of general guidelines are presented below and each partner will analyse and formulate the topics of the guidelines with additions in the excursion descriptions, based on each country specifics.

The target audience for the tour guide guidelines is:

- A. touristic offices and educators.
- B. Small groups (independent excursions)

2. Guidelines to develop a physical excursion

LEVEL 1: How to create a unique tour.

1. Define Objectives:

General Objective: To use an interactive educational experience to bring visibility to the contributions of women in Velenje and the surrounding area.

Specific Objectives:

- To create a historical and cultural route in Velenje, focusing on locations tied to significant Slovenian women.
- To educate participants on the contributions of these women to various fields such as art, science, and social activism.
- To foster a deeper cultural understanding of the role of women in shaping local and national history.

2. Define the thematic of the excursion:

The tour will focus on the diverse achievements of Slovenian women, ranging from art and literature to social activism and science. The selected locations will reflect these varied contributions.

3. Recommend a rich educational content for each woman presented:

Local tour is designed around the following women:

A Miner's Wife (Fictional) symbolizes the strength and resilience of the women who supported their families in the mining communities of Velenje. This character represents the essential role these women played in maintaining their households and the cohesion of their communities during challenging times.

Jelka Reichman (1926-2017) was a renowned Slovenian painter and illustrator, best known for her captivating illustrations in children's books. Over her career, she contributed to more than 200 book projects, making her a beloved figure in Slovenian literature. Her works continue to enchant new generations of readers in Slovenia and beyond.

Herma Groznik (1940-2022) was a dedicated teacher and a passionate advocate for scouting in Velenje. Her significant contribution to integrating scouting into primary schools earned her a prestigious municipal award, the coat of arms of the Municipality of Velenje, in 2005.

Urša Stropnik Šonc was born in Slovenj Gradec in 1973. She graduated from secondary school (natural sciences and mathematics) in Velenje and graduated in fine arts (book illustration) at

the Faculty of Arts in Maribor. Since 1998 she has been working as an independent cultural artist. Her first book illustration (a picture book by Rok Poles, *About Three Bats*) was published in 1997. In her twenty-year career, she has illustrated more than 80 books, participated in 20 solo and 10 group exhibitions, and has taken part in the Slovenian Biennial of Illustration three times.

Antonija Sternad (1873-1950) was the first trained midwife in Šoštanj, known for her exceptional service in helping deliver thousands of babies. Her work not only made her a respected figure in her community but also played a crucial role in improving healthcare in the region.

Alma Karlin (1889-1950) was a Slovenian writer, traveller, and polyglot who journeyed extensively across the world. She documented her experiences in several books, offering unique insights into the diverse cultures she encountered. Alma's adventurous spirit and literary contributions made her a significant figure in Slovenian history.

Barbara Celjska (1392-1451), also known as Barbara of Celje, was a powerful figure in medieval Europe. As the queen of Hungary, she wielded significant influence in political affairs, making her one of the most notable women of her time.

The virtual map includes additional remarkable women who left impact in Slovenian history and deserve to be mentioned. Those could be included in the national tour. Pilots and excursion within HerStory project will be done on local level.

Anica Černež (1900-1944) was a Slovenian teacher, writer, and poet who came from a family of educators. She was a dedicated teacher of mathematics, physics, and chemistry and made significant contributions to Slovenian education and literature.

Zofka Kveder (1878-1926) was a pioneering Slovenian writer and feminist. Known for her novels, short stories, and essays, she was a vocal advocate for women's rights, focusing on themes of women's lives, education, and emancipation. Her work laid the foundation for feminist literature in Slovenia.

Franja Bojc Bidovec (1913-1944) was a Slovenian nurse who played a vital role during World War II by working in a secret partisan hospital. Her bravery and dedication in treating wounded fighters under perilous conditions have cemented her legacy as a heroine in Slovenian history.

Ivana Kobilica (1861-1926) is considered Slovenia's most important painter. Her work, which reflects her deep artistic talent, played a significant role in shaping the Slovenian art scene. Ivana's paintings remain a vital part of Slovenia's cultural heritage.

Minka Govekar (1874-1950) was a Slovenian translator, activist, and publicist. She played a crucial role in advancing education and women's rights in Slovenia, leaving a lasting impact on the social and cultural landscape of her country.

Ida Kravanja (1907-1979), better known as Ita Rina, was a successful Slovenian actress who achieved international fame in the European film industry. Her career highlights the global reach and impact of Slovenian talent.

4. Define a compelling excursion tour content:

The tour focuses on women that left their impact in SAŠA region, specifically in Velenje, Šoštanj and Celje. It includes the following women and their stories. The online content is supported through discussion and questions, with aim to engage participants to share their experience and views. Competitive questions boost their interest and active participation.

LOCATION NUMBER	1
LOCATION	Miner's statue at Titov trg or Museum of Mining Velenje
WOMAN	A Miner's Wife (Fictional)
INFORMATION	<p>Fictional role: This fictional miner's wife represents the unwavering strength and resilience of the women who supported their families in the mining communities of Velenje. She symbolizes the backbone of these communities, standing as a testament to the enduring spirit of those who managed households and cared for their families while their husbands worked in the demanding and often perilous coal mines.</p> <p>This character embodies the sacrifices, hard work, and the vital role these women played in maintaining the well-being of their families and the cohesion of the mining community, making her a fitting symbol of dedication and fortitude.</p>
ACTIVITY	<p>Make a stop at miner's statue on the main square. Discuss the role of women in that period.</p> <p>Optional: you can also visit Mining Museum where the typical miner's home is displayed.</p>
QUESTIONS	<p>Kahoot!</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What role does the fictional miner's wife represent in the mining communities of Velenje? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Political leader B. Household manager (Correct) C. School teacher

	<p>D. Nurse</p> <p>2. What qualities does the statue of the miner's wife symbolize in the mining community?</p> <p>A. Strength and resilience (Correct)</p> <p>B. Wealth and luxury</p> <p>C. Independence and adventure</p> <p>D. Art and culture</p>
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LOCATION NUMBER	2
LOCATION	Academy of Fine Arts and Design (Ljubljana) or Library Velenje
WOMAN	Jelka Reichman
<p>INFORMATION</p>	<p>(1926-2017): She is a Slovenian painter and illustrator, born in Ljubljana. She is best known for her illustrations for children's books, many of which have become classics of Slovenian children's literature. She graduated from the Academy of Fine Arts in Ljubljana, where she also completed a specialisation in graphic design. She has devoted her entire creative life to children's illustration.</p> <p>Her outstanding oeuvre includes over 200 book projects and more than 2,200,000 copies of individual books in various editions. Her picture books are produced and reprinted for new generations of readers in this country and all over the world. She has been working with Mladinska knjiga since 1964.</p> <p>Her artistic career began with the illustration of Dragotin Kette's fairy tale Šivilja in škarjice / The Seamstress and the Scissors. She has also illustrated books by Josip Ribičič (Miškolin, Nana, the Little Monkey), Kajetan Kovič (My Friend Piki Jakob, Muri the Cat, Pajacek and the Doll, Drendaj the Dragon, The Golden Ship), Svetlana Makarovič (The Terrible Wolf), Leopold Suhodolčan (The Little Cepecepetavček), Miha Mate (The Toy School), Srečko</p>

	Kosovel (The Sweet Little Bears), Prežihov Voranec (Levi Devžej), Janez Bitenec (The Three Kittens), Polonce Kovač (The Little Mouse), the collection of fairy tales The Golden Bird and others. Her artwork also enriches the magazines Cicido and Ciciban. Part of her rich oeuvre is collected in the anthologies The Miracle Garden and Rasla je Jelka.
ACTIVITY	You can visit Velenje library and search some of the books she illustrated. After that you can discussed about Jelka Reichman and her work and the impact she has in the field of children's literature.
QUESTIONS	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> What is Jelka Reichman best known for? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Sculptures B. Children's book illustrations (Correct) C. Abstract paintings D. Photography Which of these books was illustrated by Jelka Reichman? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. "Harry Potter" B. "The Seamstress and the Scissors" (Correct) C. "Lord of the Rings" D. "The Great Gatsby"

LOCATION NUMBER	3
LOCATION	Rod Jezerski zmaj
WOMAN	Herma Groznik
INFORMATION	(1940-2022) Herma has been very active in shaping the local community throughout her life. She was a teacher who loved to be involved in many activities, but she had a special love for scouting and her contribution in this field was really great. Many would agree that it is to her credit that Scouting has become a part of all the primary schools in Velenje. In 2005, Hermina Groznik received a high municipal award the coat of arms of the Municipality of

	<p>Velenje for her significant contribution to the local community.</p>
<p>ACTIVITY</p>	<p>There is a building scouts currently use for regular meeting in Velenje. It's called Lukova Vila. It's in a nature a short walk from Velenje center. You can make stops on the way there in the children's park and have a talk about scouting and why Herma is so important for Velenje.</p>
<p>QUESTIONS</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What major contribution did Herma Groznic make to the schools in Velenje? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Introducing modern technology B. Integrating scouting into primary schools (Correct) C. Establishing art programs D. Organizing international exchanges 2. What award did Herma Groznic receive for her community contributions in 2005? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Nobel Prize B. Coat of arms of the Municipality of Velenje (Correct) C. National Teacher Award D. Scout of the Year

LOCATION NUMBER	4
LOCATION	Velenje Health Centre
WOMAN	Urška Stropnik Šonc
<p data-bbox="204 499 400 528">INFORMATION</p>	<p data-bbox="620 499 1390 976">Urša Stropnik Šonc was born in Slovenj Gradec in 1973. She graduated from secondary school (natural sciences and mathematics) in Velenje and graduated in fine arts (book illustration) at the Faculty of Arts in Maribor. Since 1998 she has been working as an independent cultural artist. Her first book illustration (a picture book by Rok Poles, About Three Bats) was published in 1997. In her twenty-year career, she has illustrated more than 80 books, participated in 20 solo and 10 group exhibitions, and has taken part in the Slovenian Biennial of Illustration three times.</p> <p data-bbox="620 1025 1390 1592">She collaborates with many publishing houses, e.g. Obzorja, Pivec, DZS, Didakta, Izolit, Aristej, Hieroglif, etc., and magazines such as Zmajček, Cicizabavnik, Trobentica, Dodo, BIM-BAM and others. Her contribution enriched the children's colouring books by Kristina Stropnik, which are among the best quality examples of this genre. In the framework of cooperation with museum institutions, she illustrated a guide to the museum collection of the Maribor Regional Museum for children (Tigi the Castle Kitten: A Walk Through the Maribor Regional Museum for Young Visitors, 2001) and illustrated thematic sections of the permanent installation at the Faces of Ljubljana exhibition at the Ljubljana City Museum (2003-2004).</p> <p data-bbox="620 1641 1390 2027">Her paintings adorn the paediatric wards of the Velenje Health Centre and the General Hospital of Franca Derganec in Šempeter pri Novi Gorici. She has designed wooden puzzles and toys (e.g. Animal Garden, 2010), she is the author of the art templates for the puppet show Dr. Eko performed by the FRU-FRU theatre (2010). She also works as an art pedagogue, she taught at the Nazarje Primary School in 1998, and now she teaches subjects in the field of art and design at the People's University in Velenje.</p>

ACTIVITY	Your starting point can be Velenje Health Centre, where she painted the outside wall. After that you can go to Ljudska univerza Velenje, where she also painted one of the classrooms and there you can learn about her more.
QUESTIONS	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. In which year did Urša Stropnik Šonc publish her first book illustration? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) 1995 b) 1997 (Correct) c) 1999 d) 2001 2. Which of the following institutions did Urša Stropnik Šonc create illustrations for a children's guide? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A. National Gallery of Slovenia B. Slovenian Museum of Natural History C. Museum of Contemporary Art Ljubljana D. Maribor Regional Museum (Correct)

LOCATION NUMBER	5
LOCATION	Municipality Šoštanj
WOMAN	Antonija Strnad
INFORMATION	<p>(1873-1950): Antonija Sternad, maiden name Acman, was born on 23 April 1873 to Gregor Acman and Lucia Acman. She was a famous midwife, the first in Šoštanj with a degree in midwifery. Antonija Sternad graduated from the midwifery school in Ljubljana on 29 July 1905, after completing a six-month course in midwifery organised by the Imperial-King's Foundation for the Education of Midwives.</p> <p>She helped 3000-4000 babies into the world in homes in Šoštanj and the surrounding area. Among others, Karel</p>

	<p>Destovnik Kajuh. Antonija Sternad is remembered as a very prominent citizen. According to stories, she was "half a doctor", as she also helped in the treatment of other illnesses. Antonija Sternad and her family lived in Šoštanj at house number 13, later at 1 Levstikova cesta.</p>
<p>ACTIVITY</p>	<p>You can start with the visit at Municipality Šoštanj, where nearby house is the one where Antonija Strnad was lived. Talk about childbirth in the period Antonija lived. Why was her role so important? What has changed since then?</p>
<p>QUESTIONS</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What profession did Antonija Sternad pioneer in Šoštanj? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Doctor B. Midwife (Correct) C. Teacher D. Engineer 2. Approximately how many babies did Antonija Sternad help deliver during her career? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. 500-1000 B. 1000-2000 C. 2000-3000 D. 3000-4000 (Correct)

LOCATION NUMBER	6
LOCATION	Alma Karlin statue in city Celje
WOMAN	Alma Karlin
INFORMATION	<p>(1889-1950): She was a Slovenian writer, traveller and polyglot, born in Celje. She travelled extensively around the world and wrote several books about her experiences, including "Globetrotting Through Siberia and Central Asia" and "In the Land of Silent". She finished high school in Graz, from where she went to London in 1909 to study languages. She studied English, French, Latin, Italian, Norwegian, Danish, Russian and Spanish.</p> <p>At the beginning of the First World War, in 1914, she had to flee to Sweden and Norway because, as an Austro-Hungarian citizen, she was unwelcome in London. In 1918, she returned to Celje, where she founded a school for foreign languages, and her decision to travel around the world was ripe. She used her savings to buy her first typewriter, the famous Erika, which followed her for the rest of her life. She prepared for her journey by practising her painting skills and taking additional lessons in geography, history, natural history, botany and zoology.</p>
ACTIVITY	As her statute is near railway station in Celje, you can start in railway station in Velenje. During the ride, you can talk and learn about her and her work. After reaching her statute in city Celje, you can solve some short questionnaire and check your gained knowledge.
QUESTIONS	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> What was Alma Karlin renowned for? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Painting B. Writing and traveling (Correct Answer) C. Political activism D. Teaching Which of the following books was written by Alma Karlin?

	<p>A. "In the Land of Silent" (Correct Answer)</p> <p>B. "To Kill a Mockingbird"</p> <p>C. "War and Peace"</p> <p>D. "1984"</p>
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LOCATION NUMBER	7
LOCATION	Castle in city Celje or Celje Library
WOMAN	Barbara Celjska
<p>INFORMATION</p>	<p>Barbara of Celje was born around 1392, presumably in Celje. Barbara was the youngest of six children of Count Herman II of Celje and Countess Anna of Schaunberg (d. 1396). She was brought up at the court in Celje together with her (little) cousin Anna, who married King Władysław II of Poland in 1402. Jagiel. Barbara was given an important role in her father's dynastic plans at an early age when, after the Battle of Nikopol (1396), opportunities opened up for the Celje family within the Hungarian kingdom. Herman betrothed her to the twenty-four years older King Sigismund of Hungary in 1401, they married in Krapina in November 1405, and she was crowned Queen of Hungary in Székesfehérvár on 6 December.</p>
QUESTIONS	<p>1. Who was Barbara of Celje married to?</p> <p>A. King Władysław II of Poland</p> <p>B. King Sigismund of Hungary (Correct Answer)</p> <p>C. Emperor Charles V</p> <p>D. King Henry VIII</p> <p>2. In which year did Barbara of Celje marry King Sigismund of Hungary?</p> <p>A. 1392</p> <p>B. 1401</p> <p>C. 1405 (Correct Answer)</p> <p>D. 1410</p>

5. Tour Excursion Planning:

The route is based on the geographical proximity of the selected locations and offers various implementations. The local tour includes towns Velenje, Šoštanj and Celje.

The tour starts in Velenje, with information how women are not properly represented in Velenje's history, as there are no monuments, streets etc. dedicated to female artist, scientist, musician etc. The first stop is the miners' statue, that represents mining and the role of miners in Velenje. However, the focus shifts on miner's wives, who carried the burden and responsibilities for entire families, while their husband and sons worked in mines. Despite constant battling fear and the responsibilities, taking care of families and homes they were overlooked throughout history. The tour then continues to several other locations, leading to neighbouring town Šoštanj and finally ends in Celje, whereby visiting the statue of Ana Karlin we can see good example of how a woman and her work can be respectfully represented by the city.

LEVEL 2: How to implement an exciting tour.

1. Add Interactive Elements to excursion tour:

The interactive part will be done through raising questions, engaging discussion and motivating participants to share their knowledge and opinion. To add some digital interactivity Kahoot! was prepared (as majority of participants will be very young). Audiovisual materials will support then guidance at locations where the presence of prominent women is less visually evident.

We will also use other materials such as children's books (for illustrators), some hand-on materials for Herma Groznic (camping equipment) and pictures.

After each location participants will play a game to raise their interest and encourage participation. During the piloting phase Kahoot will be used on location as groups are relatively small, but this might be adapted later after trialling phase.

Since the mobile app developed through the HerStory project is already available, it will be introduced during the tour pilot phase.

2. Verify accessibility and provide necessary information:

When selecting locations and designing the tour several accessibility aspects were considered:

- All chosen locations are accessible for all, including people with disabilities.
- As the tour included 3 towns/cities local transport schedule will be provided. For the purpose of testing mini van will be hired to bring participants to more remote locations.
- The content and the questions will be adapted for different target groups – younger participants will have a more playful experience; with older students the focus will be on discussion.
- Questionnaires will be done at the end, with support of mentors and the guide.

3. Receive Feedback and Improvement:

The feedback from participants will be collected during and after the tours. The tour will be guided by two LUV staff members, one will act as guide, another will take notes and collect feedback. This will help us to continually improve the tour experience. New monuments or developments related to women's history will be added if proposed by the participants to keep the tour content current.

4. Engage Locals through Collaborations:

- The tour includes visit to Velenje' s library and Lukova vila. It can also include Mining Museum Velenje, and Tourist information centre.
- Illustrator Urška Stropnik Šonc provides workshops for kids on regular basis and will be invited to participate at the tours.
- Local scout association can be contacted so that they will be at Lukova vila during the visit and make a short demonstration of their activities.

LEVEL 3: Generic guidelines for individual and self-guided tours.

1. Enable the customization of excursions:

- Utilize the HerStory app or other mobile tools to offer **digital interactions** at each tour stop. QR codes can be placed at each location, linking to videos, audio stories, or detailed articles about the women featured in the tour, such as Alma Karlin or Jelka Reichman. This makes the content more engaging for self-guided participants.
- Incorporate a **Quiz Feature** - participants can engage with an interactive quiz after visiting each tour stop. This could test their knowledge about Slovenian women in history, like Antonija Sternad or Urška Stropnik Šonc, providing instant feedback and making the learning experience more dynamic.
- Similar to the treasure hunt format, incorporate a **virtual scavenger hunt**. Participants could find hidden clues or solve puzzles related to each woman's life or accomplishments. The clues could be in the form of QR codes at different locations, unlocking the next stop of the tour once completed. An actual map could be created for kids to point them from one location to another.
- Offer downloadable or streamable **audio guides**, allowing participants to hear narrations at each location. This can also be interactive with sound clips or interviews from historians. This enhances the learning experience for diverse participants especially for those with migrant background.
- To increase engagement and expand the project's reach, participants could be encouraged to share their experiences on social media with a specific hashtag, posting photos or reflections about what they learned during the tour.

2. Develop options for Training Guides or/and self-guided tours:

Post-Tour Survey

After completing the tour, participants should be prompted to fill out a feedback form via the Google Form or similar. This allows for gathering feedback on the content, accessibility, and overall experience. Offering incentives like digital badges or exclusive content (e.g., extended stories or interviews) can encourage survey participation.

Real-Time Feedback on Tour Stops

Implement a system where participants can rate each tour stop, providing quick insights into what worked well and where improvements can be made. This could help adjust future tours, ensuring content remains relevant and engaging.

Collect Qualitative Feedback

The qualitative observation of participant engagement can be applied to the self-guided tour by asking participants to reflect on their experience—e.g., what surprised them, what they found most meaningful—at the end of the tour.

Highlight Participant Contributions

Involve participants in improving the tours. For instance, participants could propose new women to feature in future tours based on local suggestions, creating a more community-driven improvement process. You can also award them for their contribution.

Continuous Content Updates

Based on participant feedback, ensure that the tour is regularly updated with new insights, quiz questions, or even additional stops that reflect suggestions. For example, new locations in Velenje could be included if relevant historical figures or monuments are identified through feedback from the pilot phase.

Extra tips.

Having a QR Code printed to go to the local map of the city, so people can follow the tour or access to the guidelines to make the tour in an educational way.

Link to the HerStory virtual map

<https://map.herstoryproject.eu/>

Link to the mandatory completion EU questionnaire:

https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/CERV_2021-2027

Link to Google Questionnaire

<https://forms.office.com/Pages/ResponsePage.aspx?id=DjZ60K5mRkCtIyoHZtHBgzH8XrcF-JLp1B8xfR41k9UNEZLMURXV1pQSVAXQVILSIAXMDVZTzFLUy4u>

